

Original Article

The Role of Religious Commitments in the Life of Students

Rahat Yasmeen*¹, Dr. Sehrish Naseer²

¹Institute of Education, University of Sargodha, Sargodha

²National Research University Higher School of Economics, Russian Federation.

Abstract

Religious commitment is a prominent feature in the lives of many students in Pakistan. The major goal of current study was to examine “The role of religious commitments in the life of students”. The method used in this study was quantitative and research design was cross-sectional survey research design. The targeted population of the current study was all undergraduate students at university of Mianwali, Mianwali. The sampling technique used in the present study was convenient sampling technique. The sample were the students of three selected departments from Faculty of Social Sciences i.e., Department of Education, Department of Economics and Department of Psychology. Total data from 308 students was collected online through Google form. An adopted instrument was used in this study. “Religious Commitment Scale” was adopted to examine the students’ religious commitment. Correlation and regression analysis techniques were used for data analysis. The findings of the study produced significant relationship between religious commitment and academic performance of students and the effect of religious commitment on academic performance was also significant. It was suggested that universities should conduct seminars for the academic advancement of their students. It was recommended that universities need to prioritize the enhancement of students’ religious practices to regularize their daily activities.

Keywords: religion, religious commitment, academic performance, undergraduate and students

INTRODUCTION

In the globe, religion is major sociocultural power which help in shaping the behaviors, thoughts, action and societal norms of human. Religion has major contribution in fostering sense of purpose, infusing values and guiding behaviors. In face of academic and personal challenges, religious views and practices can help as calming elements. In present context, religious commitment a person’s devotion to Islamic beliefs, values, and practices has emerged as a vibrant part of investigation in understanding students’ academic performance.

Religious values and beliefs frequently assist in providing purpose in life and simplify psychological well-being. Different Practices i.e., God, worship, and pilgrimage promote inner satisfaction and boost good assertiveness (Alimardani et al., 2014). The study of Novinfar and Rafat, (2010) recommended that inner pleasure can be attained through focusing on divine affection, goals and spiritual values. There is positive association in psychological well-being and religious commitments between gender (Kazemianmoghadam & Mehrabizadeh, 2009). Religious commitments not only influence psychological well-being, but it also effects numerous parts of the life of human including education. It was observed that religious students

JOURNAL OF
SOCIAL HORIZONS

Copyright © The Author(s). 2025

This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribute 4.0 International License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author(s) and source are credited.

How to Cite:

Yasmeen, R., & Naseer, S. (2025). The Role of Religious Commitments in the Life of Students. *Journal of Social Horizons*, 2(3), 388-395.

* Corresponding Author: Rahat Yasmeen | Institute of Education, University of Sargodha, Sargodha

✉ rahatniazi257@gmail.com

© 2025 | College of Education, Swabi, Pakistan.

perform better in academics because religious life attaches them with values (Glass & Jacobs, 2005). In educational attainment religiosity provides useful alternatives and decision-making frameworks for the students (Lehrer, 2004). However, religion is multidimensional aspect, and it has positive as well as negative impacts. Some elements of religion positively develop academic performance, and some may block academic performance. Accordingly, thoughtful religious commitment's nuanced impact on students' academic lives remains a complex but vital research concern (Achour et al., 2017)

In literature, religious commitment is interchangeably used in terms of religious involvement, orientation, and religiosity (Khenfer & Roux, 2012). Religious commitment is "the degree to which a person adheres to his or her religious values, beliefs, and practices, and uses them in daily living," (Schumann, 2020; Worthington et al., 2003). According to Musgrave and McFarlane (2004), in daily practices, religiosity includes both the significance individuals ascribe to their beliefs and the way those beliefs are manifested. In the perspective of Islam, religiosity is profoundly rooted in the concept of *taqwa*, or consciousness of God. The fulfillment of God's rights, protection of the rights of others, moral conduct, and performance of religious obligations such as prayer, fasting, and charity is described as religiosity. According to Gazzali (2004), without sincere devotion, these rituals may become dull, losing their transformative ability. Individuals considered truly religious are those who internalize their faith and reflect it in their actions and decisions (Achour et al., 2017). The integrated belief system of religion supports individuals to deal with issues of meaning, mortality, and community (Dengah, 2017). It fulfills the human need for social consistency and rule-based living, which in turn forms health, behavior, and life decisions (Baumeister et al., 2010). Religious commitment helps in buffering from anxiety and guide decision-making in stressful circumstances. These factors are directly relevant to academic environments (Wilson et al., 2021).

According to Worthington's (1988), religious commitments theorize that individuals who are highly religious spend their life by following religious values, integrating their faith into their world view. According to this perception, highly committed students are more likely to show ethical academic behavior and consistent motivation. The human capital model developed by Lehrer (2005), also supports that religious commitments play role in academic progress and personal development of students. Religious commitments have significant impact on the educational experiences and outcomes of the students (Chukwuorji et al., 2017). Milot and Ludden (2009), observed that religious commitment in rural adolescent students reported higher religious importance exhibited better behavior in school, greater motivation, and higher academic performance (Chukwuorji et al., 2017). The National Study of Youth and Religion, as reported in *Soul Searching* by Smith and Denton (2005), concluded that highly religious committed teens perform better in life domains including academics compared to their less religious committed peers. Previous studies have used tools such the Religious Commitment Inventory 10 by Worthington et al. (2003), King and Hunt's (1969), Basic Religious Scales, and Glock and Stark's (1965), Dimensions of Religious Commitment to describe religious commitment. These instruments allow for comprehensive measurement of religious orientation, offering valuable insight into the mechanisms through which faith might influence academic behavior.

In society students are considered the intellectual and spiritual assets. The academic performance of the pupils not only relies on cognitive competencies and instructional value as well as on emotive strength, motivation, and social support systems. Religion is source of peace and comfort and that is important for academic stability and emotive strength, motivation, and social support systems (Mohammadi et al., 2016). Religion also boosts pupils' sense of individuality, regularity, and commitment, and all of these are associated with academic performance. The beneficial effects of religiosity have been particularly emphasized during adolescence, a critical period for identity formation and moral development. According to Hardy and King (2019), religion provides a framework for character building, which in turn fosters academic and life satisfaction. Strengths of character, often cultivated through religious teachings, are positively associated with subjective well-being (Wnuk, 2021).

Despite the growing body of literature linking religion to academic outcomes, there remain significant gaps in understanding how specific dimensions of religious commitment affect students'

educational routes. Cultural and contextual factors can also moderate this relationship, making it necessary to explore these dynamics in diverse educational and religious settings. Moreover, as religious society continues to evolve alongside changes in societal values and educational systems, contemporary investigations are needed to understand its relevance and application in the lives of modern students. In the context of Pakistan, where religion plays an integral role in the personal, cultural, and educational lives of individuals, understanding the effect of religious commitment on students' educational performance is both timely and essential. Despite the emphasis placed on academic success by educational institutions, limited research has been conducted in Pakistan to explore how internalized religious values, beliefs, and practices may shape students' learning attitudes, motivation, behavior, and performance.

Religion in Pakistani society is not only a personal belief system but also a social and moral framework that influences daily decision-making, discipline, goal setting, and community life. For students, especially those navigating academic pressures, religious commitment may serve as a coping mechanism and a source of moral direction. It has the potential to enhance traits such as perseverance, self-regulation, and responsibility characteristics closely linked with academic achievement.

Therefore, this study aims to explore the role of religious commitment in shaping students' academic performance. It seeks to investigate how religious values, beliefs, and practices influence academic engagement, motivation, and achievement. By examining these relationships, the study hopes to provide meaningful insights into the role of faith in educational development and contribute to the broader discourse on religion and youth well-being.

Objectives:

Following were the objectives of the current research:

1. To find out the relationship between religious commitment and academic performance of students
2. To find out the effect of religious commitment on the academic performance of students

Research Hypotheses:

Following were the hypothesis of the current research:

1. H_{A1}: There is significant relationship between relationship between religious commitment and academic performance of students
2. H_{A2}: There is a significant effect of religious commitment on the academic performance of students

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The role of research design in a research study is as a bridge by which researcher reaches at the destination in order to achieve the predefined goals. Research design tells about the plan of the study so as which type of study researcher is going to conduct either quantitative or qualitative. There are many research design like Experimental research design, Correlational research design, Causal- comparative and Cross-sectional survey research design and many more (Fraenkel et al., 2012). For the present study, cross-sectional survey design was considered more suitable by following the quantitative research method.

Population of the study

The population of the current research was all undergraduate students of University of Mianwali.

Sampling and Sample

Convenient sampling method was used in current study. The sample of the study was the undergraduate students from Faculty of Social Sciences. Three departments (Department of Education, Department of Economics and Department of Psychology) were selected conveniently. The total sample of current study was 300 B.S students of semester 2nd, 6th and 8th.

Research instruments

Data was gathered through Google form and for this purpose an adopted instrument of “The Religious Commitment Inventory” developed by Worthington et al. (2003), was used. The Religious Commitment

Inventory contained 10 items, and it was used to collect data from respondents to know their opinion about their religious commitments. Likert scale ranging from 1 (Not at all true of me) to 5 (Totally true of me) was used for the Religious Commitment Inventory. Religious commitment was independent variable and academic performance dependent variable was measured through Cumulative Grade Point Average.

Pilot Testing

Pilot testing is used to make necessary changes in research tools on the basis of the small number of respondents from sample (Hassan et al., 2006). Pilot testing was carried out to check research instruments. The purpose of the pilot testing was to know that the instruments were valid and reliable for students. Validity and reliability of the instruments was checked through pilot testing. Five instructors from the psychology and education departments at the University of Mianwali in Mianwali were consulted in order to validate the instruments. Following instrument validation, 26 students' data were used for pilot testing. The Religious Commitment Inventory instruments were valid and highly reliable. As alpha was .621.

Data Collection Procedures

The questionnaires were filled in by the students online by using Google Form. The data collected were entered into the computer for analysis.

Data analysis

Although the data was gathered via a Google form, the researchers addressed missing data by adjusting the privacy settings so that participants had to complete each item; if they skipped one, they would not be able to move on to the next one. In the current investigation, regression and correlation analysis techniques were applied. SPSS version 24 was used to evaluate the data.

Ethics statement

The study involving human subjects did not require ethical review or approval in accordance with local laws and institutional procedures. However, all other ethical requirements were met during the preparation of this paper, and participants' written consent was obtained; as a result, responders (who were simply volunteers) were notified and involved in the data gathering process. Respondents were reassured by researchers that their information would be kept private and that the study would only be utilized for research purposes. Additionally, respondents were able to discontinue the study at any time if they were not happy with it.

RESULTS

Correlation analysis

Table 1. relationship between religious commitments and academic performance of students

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Academic performance</i>	
Religious Commitment	Pearson Correlation	.13*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.01
	N	8308

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The association between respondents' academic achievement and their religious commitment was displayed in Table 1. Academic achievement and religious commitment had a small but statistically significant link, according to the Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = .13$, $P = .01$). It indicates a correlation between academic achievement and religious conviction. Researcher agreed with the alternative hypothesis

that "there is a significant relationship between religious commitment and academic performance" in its relation to academic performance.

Linear Regression Analysis

Linear regression analysis is a statistical tool to check the impact of independent variable on outcome variables (Xiang, 2020).

Table 2. Effect of religious commitments and academic performance of students

Model summary of Linear Regression Analysis

<i>R</i>	<i>R</i> ²	<i>F</i>	<i>Adjusted R</i> ²	<i>S. E</i>
.137 ^a	.019	5.82	.015	.501

Model summary reflected in table 2 value of ($F = 5.82$, $R^2 = .019$) R^2 is .019 means 1.9 % of variation from depended on variable (Academic performance) can be explained by variation in the independent variable (religious commitment). Acceptable value of R square for social sciences is up to 40% (Chaudhry & Niazi, 2017). The remaining 98.1% can be explained by further factors that are not in the model. With these results it can be concluded that religious commitment has no predictive powers, as this variable count 1.9 % of variation in academic performance.

Table 3. Linear Regression Analysis of religious commitments and academic performance of students

Coefficients					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardize Coefficients	<i>t</i>	Sig.
	Beta	Std. Error	<i>B</i>		
(Constant)	2.75	.16		17.05	.000
Religious Commitments	.012	.00	.13	2.41	.016

Table 3 indicates that the model's parameter is significant based on coefficient regression. The Religious Commitments parameter, or β , is significant for the above coefficients table, with a P value of .016. The alternative hypothesis, which states that there is a statistically significant impact of religious commitments on students' academic performance, is going to be accepted given the coefficients ($\beta = .012 \neq 0$) and beta not equal to zero (0 coefficients indicate that the value of the dependent variable does not consistently differ as the value of the independent variable increases).

Discussions

Current study examined the role of religious commitments in the life of students. Results of present study showed that religious commitment has positive significant relationship between religious commitment and academic performance of undergraduate students. The study Regnerus (2000), study results were in support of current research that the youngsters who regularly perform religious services and placed importance on their faith showed higher academic achievement. The author accredited this to the values of discipline, community support, and future orientation reinforced by religious participation. Zern (1989), reported mixed findings, showing that while religious participation had some positive significant correlation with GPA and contradicted current research. The study of ELMS (2017), produced significant relationship between religion and academic performance. Another study results also favored the current research results as there is link between individual religious affiliation and academic performance (Toldson & Andersonz, 2010). The study of Wallace et al. (2003), contradicted the current study as its findings suggested that religious commitment all alone cannot predict the academic achievement. This study was conducted on the

American students of 9th and 10th grade. Another study results also not supported the current research findings as JEYNES (2005), reported insignificant relationship in students attending religious revival services and academic outcomes. In the study of Everitt (2011), insignificant positive relationship was found between Academic Attitude and the religious orientation.

Another result of current research showed that the effect of religious commitment on academic performance of undergraduate students was significant. Another study results were in support of current research as Jeynes (2003), performed a meta-analysis examining the influence of religious commitment on student academic performance. The results indicated a positive correlation, especially among minority students. The moral guidance, reduction in risky behaviors, and structured life provided by religion were cited as contributing factors. The study of Glanville et al. (2008), showed and minor effect of religious commitment and academic grades. According to Regnerus (2000), religious beliefs worked as strong motivating factor in academic learning. The study of Horwitz (2020) showed an insignificant effect between academic performance and religious commitment.

Conclusion

The goal of the current study was to determine how students' religious affiliations affected their lives. Based on the findings, it was determined that undergraduate students' academic achievement and their religious commitment were significantly correlated. Undergraduate students' academic performance was significantly impacted by their religious commitment.

Recommendations

In future studies, longitudinal research design may be used to clearly understand the directions of religious commitment as well as academic success. In future it would be important to know the level of religious commitment and academic performance of students at university level. Furthermore, it is recommended that in order to assess religious commitment, students' perspective may be measured to gain different results. More universities may be included in sample for more generalizability of the results with change over time. In future studies other religions may be considered as in current research only religion Islam is considered.

Acknowledgments

Authors pays heartiest gratefulness to Worthington et al. for giving permission to use their instrument "Religious Commitment Inventory". The authors would like to thank Prof. Dr. Ashfaque Ahmad SHAH, Dr. Syeda Zunaira Fatima, respected teachers, and respondents, for their valuable suggestions during the conduct and completion of research and during the entire study they extended all facilities for this research work. We are also extremely grateful to our family for their love, prayers, care and sacrifices.

Conflict of interest:

All authors have no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- Achour, M., Mohd Nor, M. R., Amel, B., Bin Seman, H. M., & MohdYusoff, M. Y. Z. (2017). Religious commitment and its relation to happiness among Muslim students: The educational level as moderator. *Journal of religion and health*, 56, 1870-1889.
- Alimardani, A., Alimardani, M., Beni, M. A., & Shajie, K. (2014). Relationship between religious attitude and happiness of physical education students of University of Qom. *International Journal of Sport Studies*, 4(7), 783-788.
- Baumeister, R. F., Vohs, K. D., & Oettingen, G. (2016). Pragmatic prospection: How and why people think about the future. *Review of general psychology*, 20(1), 3-16.
- Chaudhry, M. A., & Niazi, H. K. (2017). *Job Stress of Academia and Its Effect On Their Performance In Public Sector Universities Of Punjab Department of Educational Planning , Policy Studies and*

Leadership Faculty Allama Iqbal Open University Job Stress Of Academia And Its Effect On Their Performance.

- Chukwuorji, J. C., Ituma, E. A., & Ugwu, L. E. (2018). Locus of control and academic engagement: Mediating role of religious commitment. *Current Psychology*, 37, 792-802.
- Dengah, H. F. (2017). Religion as cultural models: Developing an emic measure of religiosity. *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion*, 56(1), 104-125.
- Elms, R. T. (2007). *The Role of Religiosity in Academic Success*. Washington: Washington State University.
- Enayat Novinfar, A., & Heydari Rafat, A. (2010). The relationship between religious attitude and happiness among the students of Tarbiat Modarres University. *Journal of Psychology of Religion*, 3(4), 61-72.
- Everitt, L. (2011). *Relationships between religious orientation and academic attitudes*. Virginia Consortium for Professional Psychology (Old Dominion University, College of William and Mary, Eastern Virginia Medical School, & Norfolk State University).
- Fraenkel, J., Wallen, N., & Hyun, H. (1993). *How to Design and Evaluate Research in Education 10th ed.* McGraw-Hill Education.
- Ghazali, M. (2004). *Khuluk Almuslim (Muslim's behavior)*. Damascus: Dar Alkalam.
- Glanville, J. L., Sikkink, D., & Hernandez, E. I. (2008). Religious involvement and educational outcomes: The role of social capital and extracurricular participation. *The Sociological Quarterly*, 49(1), 105-137.
- Glass, J., & Jacobs, J. (2005). Childhood religious conservatism and adult attainment among black and white women. *Social Forces*, 84(1), 555-579.
- Glock, C. Y., & Stark, R. (1965). Religion and society in tension.
- Hardy, S. A., & King, P. E. (2019). Processes of religious and spiritual influence in adolescence: Introduction to a special section. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 29(2), 244-253.
- Hassan, Z. A., Schattner, P., & Mazza, D. (2006). Doing A Pilot Study: Why Is It Essential? *Malaysian Family Physician : The Official Journal of the Academy of Family Physicians of Malaysia*, 1(2-3), 70-73.
<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/27570591>
<http://www.pubmedcentral.nih.gov/articlerender.fcgi?artid=PMC4453116>
- Horwitz, I. M. (2021). Religion and academic achievement: a research review spanning secondary school and higher education. *Review of religious research*, 63(1), 107-154.
- Jeynes, W. H. (2003). The effects of religious commitment on the academic achievement of urban and other children. *Education and Urban Society*, 36(1), 44-62.
- Jeynes, W. H. (2005). The relationship between urban students attending religious revival services and academic and social outcomes. *Education and urban society*, 38(1), 3-20.
- Kazemianmoghadam, K., & Mehrabizadeh, M. (2009). Studying relationship between religious attitude and happiness and mental health of female and male students of Behbahan Azad University. *Psychology and Religion Publication*, 2(4), 157-174.
- Khenfer, J., & Roux, E. (2012, May). How does religion matter in the marketplace for minority settings? The case of Muslim consumers in France. In *EMAC 42nd Conference* (pp. 1-7).
- King, M. B., & Hunt, R. A. (1969). Measuring the religious variable: Amended findings. *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion*, 8(2), 321-323.
- Lehrer, E. (2004). Religiosity as a determinant of educational attainment: The case of conservative Protestant women in the United States. *Review of Economics of the Household*, 2, 203-219.

- Lehrer, E. L. (2005). *Religious affiliation and participation as determinants of women's educational attainment and wages*. IZA.
- Milot, A. S., & Ludden, A. B. (2009). The effects of religion and gender on well-being, substance use, and academic engagement among rural adolescents. *Youth & Society, 40*(3), 403-425.
- Mohammadi, H., Mortazavi, M. A., Mousavi, M. R., Javanmard, Q., & Monfaredi, A. (2016). Determination of the relationship between Religious commitment and mental health among engineering students of Bonab University. *Journal of Research on Religion & Health, 2*(2), 44-53.
- Musgrave, C. F., & McFarlane, E. A. (2004, March). Israeli oncology nurses' religiosity, spiritual well-being, and attitudes toward spiritual care: a path analysis. In *oncology nursing forum* (Vol. 31, No. 2).
- Regnerus, M. D. (2000). Shaping schooling success: Religious socialization and educational outcomes in metropolitan public schools. *Journal for the scientific study of religion, 39*(3), 363-370.
- Schumann, K. (2020). A force for good: When and why religion predicts prosocial behavior. *Journal of Moral Theology, 9*(1), 34–50.
- Smith, C. & Denton, M. L. (2005). *Soul searching: The religious and spiritual lives of American teenagers*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- Toldson, I. A., & Anderson, K. A. (2010). Editor's comment: The role of religion in promoting academic success for Black students. *Journal of Negro Education, 79*(3), 205-213.
- Wallace Jr, J. M., Forman, T. A., Caldwell, C. H., & Willis, D. S. (2003). Religion and US secondary school students: Current patterns, recent trends, and sociodemographic correlates. *Youth & Society, 35*(1), 98-125.
- Wilson, A., Khumalo, I. P., & Mpofo, E. (2022). Meaning in life among Ghanaian university students: does religious commitment matter?. *Journal of religion and health, 61*(3), 2482-2499.
- Wnuk, M. (2021). Links between faith and some strengths of character: Religious commitment manifestations as a moderators. *Religions, 12*(9), 786.
- Worthington, E. L. (1988). Understanding the values of religious clients: A model and its application to counseling. *Journal of Counseling Psychology, 35*(2), 166.
- Worthington, E. L. Jr, Wade, N. G., Hight, T. L., Ripley, J. S., McCullough, M. E., Berry, J. W., Schmitt, M. M., Berry, J. T., Bursley, K. H., & O'Conner, L. (2003). The religious commitment inventory-10: Development, refinement, and validation of a brief scale for research and counseling. *Journal of Counseling Psychology, 50*(1), 84–96. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0022-0167.50.1.84>
- Xiang, Y. (2020). *The Impacts of the Modifiable Areal Unit Problem (MAUP) on Linear Regression* (Doctoral dissertation, State University of New York at Buffalo).
- Zern, D. S. (1989). Some connections between increasing religiosity and academic performance among college students. *Journal of Psychology and Theology, 17*(1), 18–24.